

Robust Image Watermarking using Content Descriptors for Security Applications in Discrete Cosine Transform Domain

Shedole Sambhaji M.¹ and V. Santhi²

^{1,2}*School of Computer Science and Engineering,
Vellore Institute of Technology, Tamil Nadu, India,*

¹*Email: sambhajis.maruthirao2015@vit.ac.in*

²*Email: vsanthi@vit.ac.in*

Abstract:

*The grayscale cover image's brightness, edge, texture, and corners coefficients are employed in the proposed work to create a mask that will be used to place the watermark. This suggested approach also uses a grayscale image as a digital watermark that is about the same size as the cover image. The cover picture is divided into 8x8 blocks in the proposed technique, and the luminance, edges, and corners coefficients are computed in the spatial domain for each block. The frequency domain is used to calculate texture coefficients for each block of the cover image. Using texture, edge, and corner coefficients, the initial level of Just Noticeable Distortion (JND) mask values (J1) are computed, and the final value of JND mask values (J2) are computed using both the J1 values and the texture coefficients. Discrete Cosine Transformed (DCT) and 8*8 block division are also used to transform the watermark image that is being examined in this proposal. Using content descriptors to build the Just Noticeable Distortion (JND) mask, the watermark is added. With numerous test images, including Lina, Barbara, Boat, Rice, Cameraman, and Pills, the suggested robust watermarking algorithm is evaluated by Mean Square Error (MSE), Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR), Bit Error Ratio (BER), Normalized Correlation Coefficient (NCC), and other qualitative metrics are used to assess the quality of watermarked images.*

Keywords: *Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR), Just Noticeable Distortion (JND), Robust Watermarking, Human Visual System (HVS), and Correlation.*

1. Introduction

The process of digitizing information content is inevitable in the current digital age. Consequently, it's important to safeguard the content of digitalized material from theft and unauthorized access. [1] [2] [3]. Digital watermarking is a technology that was developed to safeguard digital files from theft and improper manipulation. [4][5]. In order to protect a cover picture from being illegally altered, such as by copying it without authorization, producing illicit copies, or duplicating digital content, digital watermarking (DW) embeds hidden data into the image [6].[7][8]. Digital watermarking is the process of concealing a piece of digital data [9][10][11]. An audio clip, picture, logo, or bit stream might be used as the digital watermark [12] [13].

Watermarks could be added to cover data during the digital watermarking process either in the spatial domain or in the frequency domain [17][18]. Transformation methods like Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT),

and Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) could be utilized to convert the digital cover data into the frequency domain [19] [20][21]. The frequency domain watermarking approaches are more resistant to low pass and high pass filtering attacks on signal processing[22][23]. The implanted watermark is more reliable than spatial domain watermarking methods in the frequency domain because it covers the complete frequency spectrum of the cover image [24].

Figure 1 depicts the schematic for the generic watermarking system. The embedding technique uses cover image I and watermark image W as inputs to create watermarked picture I' . The watermarked picture I' may be vulnerable to malicious or unintentional attacks both during transmission and while being attempted to be stored in system memory. If a watermarked image is vulnerable to any malicious or accidental attacks, its content will be changed and I' will then "become I'' ". The image I'' serves as the input image for the watermark extraction method, which also extracts the watermark from the original cover image [25].

Equation (1) can be used to represent the watermark embedding process. The watermark extraction process is shown in Equation (2)

$$I' = \beta I + \alpha W \tag{1}$$

Where

β = Embedding factor

α = Scaling factor

I = Covered Image

W = Watermarking Image

I' = Watermarked Image

$$W = (I' - \beta I) / \alpha \tag{2}$$

Figure 1: General watermarking Scheme

A brief review of the literature on reliable digital watermarking has been done in section 2 and is presented in this part. The suggested algorithm is described in detail in section 3, and the results are shown in part 4. The intended work is concluded in Section 5.

2. Literature Review

In the following section, an overview of the literature on reliable digital watermarking methods has been conducted and is described in depth.

Mohammad Awrangjeb and Guojun Lu [26] proposed a cover image undergoes geometric alteration before the watermark is placed. Because no one can access the copyright information to verify it, the system is more secure. The suggested approach separates the image into blocks in order to extract features that are later used for the watermark placement. The suggested solution is demonstrated to be resistant to affine transformation and various signal processing attacks using a variety of techniques.

Eduardo Fragoso-Navarro and et.al [27] have proposed four evaluation criteria for visible watermarking algorithms, where the global visibility, global obtrusiveness, local obtrusiveness in the host edge region, and a global quality of the watermarked image are assessed using a few standards derived from the human visual system and a pixel-based just-noticeable distortion function. The evaluation findings demonstrate the validity of the suggested metrics for assessing the aforementioned factors in a variety of visible watermarking circumstances as well as in a number of cases when an attempt was made to eliminate the watermark sequence from the watermarked content. 59% of the pixels are not seen in this instance, according to the global visibility V , which is equal to 0.41. Both the global and edge region obtrusiveness are 1.46 104 and 1.79 105, respectively.

Arvind Kumar Parthasarathy and Subhash Kak [28] This algorithm's suggested watermark is a pseudo-random sequence watermark. In order to make the watermark less visible to the human eye, the mask was created with the assistance of the human visual system (HVS). The frequency domain watermark is included to increase the algorithm's robustness. After employing picture compression and filtering attacks, improved results were obtained. It is discovered that the weighted peak signal-to-noise ratio (WPSNR) is 38.99 dB.

Amir Najafi and et.al [29] proposed a watermarking method that employs the spread spectrum approach with a binary-coded watermark. The suggested algorithm employed a non-blind, content-based technique for watermarking images. The HVS property has been used to enhance embedding performance within the high-energy domain. It increases resistance to lossy attack types and guards against host or cover image deterioration. Based on its ability to extract watermarks accurately and watermarking capability, the suggested algorithm was assessed.

Selena Kay and Ebroul Izquierdo [30] have presented a watermarking method that combines approaches from the spatial and frequency domains. As a result, the algorithm is resistant to geometric deformation and picture processing. To insert a pseudo-random signal, Just Noticeable Distortion (JND) was calculated and employed. Robustness against image processing attacks is guaranteed via frequency domain watermarking.

The proposed technique was tested and the outcomes of popular assaults, such as geometric picture manipulation, were shown.

Mohan S Kankanhalli and et.al [31] has proposed a reliable and unnoticeable picture watermarking system that is easily expanded to video. They have suggested a novel approach that uses local content descriptors for analyzing the noise sensitivity of each individual pixel. Utilizing content descriptors including edge, brightness, and texture information, JND masks were produced. Each watermark bit is dispersed spatially, and the pseudo-noise sequence has an additional impact. The insertion's amplitude was maintained below the pixel's noise sensitivity. According to experimental findings, the watermark was immune to a number of attacks, including cropping, JPEG compression, and the inclusion of noise. The implanted watermark's perceptual invisibility has been proven.

Xiaojun Qi and Ji Qi [32] have presented a content-based image watermarking technique that was created to be resistant to geometrical and image processing attacks. A texture-based adaptive Harries corner detector determined the image's content. Work is now more resistant to attacks thanks to this functionality. To improve detection accuracy and increase robustness, the watermark has been encoded using spread spectrum technology and error-correcting code. The Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), which guarantees improved visual quality combined with stability, was used to apply the adaptive embedding strategy. The total number of matches between recoverable and embedded watermarks was used for watermark detection. The proposed technique was shown to be resistant to geometrical and signal processing challenges such quantization, compression, filtering, and augmentation. In comparison to several peers mentioned in the literature, the estimated results demonstrated greater performance.

Zhihua Xie and et. al [33] have proposed a Ridgeley domain watermark extraction and embedding technique. The programmer first divides the image into smaller chunks, and then groups the blocks according to their different textures. The middle frequencies of the RT sub-bands are chosen based on the statistical characteristics of the column coefficient after applying the Ridgeley Transform (RT) are discovered for their directional energetic property boost resilience against noise. The watermarks were intentionally included into the block's primary energy directions using a robust texture that is often less perceptible to the human eye. The local component adaptively determines the embedded watermark's strength, ensuring the watermark's invisibility. It was discovered that the work's results were resistant to noise, deletion or removal, and numerous insensitive attacks.

Bas and et.al [34] By using content-based techniques instead of pixel-based ones, author have changed the watermarking paradigm. The author has provided a summary of many methods in the spatial and frequency domains. He has also provided an outline of content-based strategies to increase the mark's imperceptibility. Utilizing feature detection, the content-based technique synchronizes the watermark after picture processing.

Wang, XY et al. [35] has tackled desynchronization, the most crucial attack problem in watermarking; if it fails, the watermark will be wrongly identified. On the basis of a multi-scale SIFT (Scale Invariant Feature Transform) detector and a local picture histogram shape in variance, content-based techniques were presented. This method

was discovered to have decent resilience to desynchronization attacks and good visual quality. The task involved employing a multi-scale SIFT detector to extract stable picture points of feature from the host image. The feature scale theory was used to create local feature regions (LFR).LFR was subjected to Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). The selected DFT amplitude allowed for the extraction of a local picture histogram.

According to the literature review, it is clear that creating a reliable watermarking algorithm is crucial since the hidden watermark is crucial for demonstrating the legal ownership of electronically stored contents. Additionally, the quality of the cover image is properly kept if the image's content is taken into consideration when determining how much modification the image can sustain.

3. Proposed Robust watermarking algorithm

This section includes a detailed explanation of a novel, reliable digital watermarking algorithm that uses content descriptors. The watermark embedding and extraction techniques make up the two portions of the proposed algorithm. In this proposal, just noticeable distortion mask is generated using content descriptors of cover image such as edge details, luminance values, texture information, and corner details. These content descriptors such as edge details, luminance value and corner details are calculated in spatial domains whereas texture information is calculated in frequency domains. The generated mask is being used to insert a watermark in the cover image in the frequency domain. The discrete cosine transformation method is used to translate the cover image I and watermark image W into frequency components. The cover and watermark images are treated as grayscale images in the presented robust digital image watermarking technique, and both images are partitioned into 8×8 blocks for the purpose of adding the watermark. The insertion and extraction of the watermark is done in the frequency domain. Figure 2 depicts the flow diagram of the suggested resilient watermarking algorithm. The next sections cover the key methods that make up the suggested algorithm.

Figure 2. Flow Diagram of Proposed Watermarking Algorithm

3.1 Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT)

The Cosine functions of various frequencies are used as kernels in the widely used discrete cosine transform (DCT), which transforms signals. A transformation method called the DCT is utilized to decorrelate the intensity values and turn them into frequency components. The DC and AC coefficients are regarded as the frequency components. The input signal is represented by the DCT transformation technique as a linear combination of its basis functions. Equation (3) provides the one-dimensional DCT forward transformation method. This transformation method is known as N point 1D - DCT. In Equation (4), the inverse transformation method is described.

$$F(u) = \left(\frac{2}{N}\right)^{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \Lambda(u) \cos \left[\frac{\pi u}{2N} (2i + 1) f(i) \right] \tag{3}$$

$$f(i) = F'(u) = \left(\frac{2}{N}\right)^{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \Lambda(u) \cos \left[\frac{\pi u}{2N} (2i + 1) f(i) \right] \tag{4}$$

where $\Lambda(\xi) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \text{for } \xi = 0 \\ 1 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$

For example, the 2D - DCT generates 8 8 coefficients for an 8 8 block of 8-bit pixels that contain both AC and DC coefficients. The DCT represents the entire pixel intensity values of a block into fewer low frequency coefficients and many high frequency components with zero values and hence it is predominantly used in data compression applications. In order to convert an image matrix into frequency components, we have to use 2D – DCT technique. The 2D – DCT forward transformation technique is given in Equation (5). The 2D- inverse transformation technique is given in Equation (6).

$$S(u, v) = C(u)C(v) \sum_{x=0}^{Z-1} \sum_{y=0}^{Z-1} s(x, y) \cos \left(\frac{(2x+1)u\pi}{2Z} \right) \cos \left(\frac{(2y+1)v\pi}{2Z} \right) \tag{5}$$

$$s'(u, v) = C(u)C(v) \sum_{x=0}^{Z-1} \sum_{y=0}^{Z-1} s(x, y) \cos \left(\frac{(2x+1)u\pi}{2Z} \right) \cos \left(\frac{(2y+1)v\pi}{2Z} \right) \tag{6}$$

3.2 Process for creating a Just Noticeable Distortion (JND) mask

Just Perceptible The term "distortion" refers to the observer's capacity to recognize noise or distortion in the field of view [28]. The spatial and frequency domains of the image content are analyzed to determine distortion sensitivity (JND), which helps to determine the maximum amount that a pixel value may be changed without significantly changing JND. The texture, brightness, edge, and corner information of the content are used to build the JND mask in the proposed work [37]. Each block receives the weight determined from these attributes. Maintaining the signal amplitude below the noise distortion sensitivity level will modulate the watermark that will be added. The cover image is separated into 8x8 non-overlapping sections, and the spatial domain calculations for the necessary content descriptors are performed. Every block must be transformed into frequency components using 2D-DCT, as illustrated in Equation (5), in order to recover the texture information. Pixel intensity data can be

correlated into frequency components using discrete cosine transformation (DCT). The spatial domain signal energy is represented by DCT as low frequency components and numerous high frequency components. [39]. We create the first mask using Equation (7) after receiving the four values for the texture, edge, corners, and brightness.

$$J_{I=M_T-\frac{1}{2}(M_E+M_C)} \quad (7)$$

The mid-gray area is where the human visual system is most sensitive to changes in intensity, and it should be observed that this sensitivity breaks down parabolically towards both ends of the grey scale. As a result, the original JND parameter value is corrected, and Equation (8) is used to determine the final JND parameter value for each block.

$$J_F = J_I + (128 - M_L)^2 \quad (8)$$

where J_I is the beginning value for the JND parameter and M_L is the mean luminance value for the block under consideration. A different approach is to multiply the DCT coefficient, the JND value J_I obtained above, and the luminance factor D_L at the moment of watermark embedding. The JND value for each block is essentially calculated by examining attributes like texture from the frequency domain and some fundamental properties taken from the spatial domain, notably edge, corner, and average brightness value. The content descriptors used in this proposal are texture information, luminance data, edge details and corner information.

Texture: The visual quality of an object's surface that is visible in a picture in connection to tone, depth, and shape is referred to as texture. We first directly extract the texture information by analyzing the DCT coefficients after they have been acquired. The DCT coefficients are used to calculate this information, which is derived from a visual model with a frequency-sensitive, image-independent component. Each 8*8 block, which consists of 64 DCT coefficients, is examined. As is well known, the strength of the signal concentrates in the high-frequency components in areas with highly textured surfaces or along edges, whereas the energy is focused in the low-frequency components in regions where the image is uniform. Using the formula Equation (9), we can calculate a measure for the texture data contained within each block based on the amount of energy included in the ac coefficients. Using Equation (9) for each 8x8 block, determine the texture information contained within each block. [28] [40].

$$P_T = \log(\sum_{i=1}^{63} v_i^2 v_0^2) \quad (9)$$

Where the 64 DCT coefficients for the 8*8 block under consideration are $v_i, i = 0, 1, \dots, 63$. It is important to note that while determining the texture value, the value of the dc component of the DCT coefficients is not taken into account. The acquired values are then scaled to the range [0, 64] for each block before being normalized and assigned to the respective blocks. Therefore, for a 512*512 image matrix, we will obtain a 64*64 matrix where each of the values corresponds to the texture data of each 8*8 block. Find scaled information between [0,64] first, and then use Equation (10) to assign normalized values to certain blocks.

$$M_T = \frac{64 * P_T}{\max(P_T)} \quad (10)$$

Luminance: It is described as how the human eye interprets the brightness of various colors. This characteristic affects how the human eye interprets the information contained in images. The frequency domain, which uses the Watson model's DC component of the DCT coefficients, and the pixel domain are the two possible domains in which to calculate this factor. The average brightness of the block is determined by the DC component, which also includes important information about the luminance in the block. Equation (11) estimates this local block's mean brightness value.

$$D_L = \left\{ \frac{DC_b}{DC_{mean}} \right\}^\alpha \quad (11)$$

The parameter used to regulate the luminance sensitivity is represented as α , where DC_b represents the DC coefficient of the DCT for block b, DC_{mean} represents the DC coefficient of the mean brightness of the display

In accordance with the authors' model, α is set to 0.649. The brightness factor is partially picture dependent because it is generated in the frequency domain according to the Watson model in addition to in the pixel domain. This is done by examining the pixels in the block. Our method makes use of the brightness factor, which is determined by calculating the average grayscale picture pixel value for that block using Equation (12).

$$M_L = \frac{P_L}{64} \quad (12)$$

Where P_L the average of the luminance is values inside the block under consideration, and M_L is the total of all the pixel values within the block. As they are acquired directly by analyzing the pixels in the spatial domain, the factors derived from the image's corners, edges, and brightness values combined are referred to as the spatial masking values..

Edges: The edges of the pixels are retrieved, and the quantity of watermark data that may be inserted into the image can be calculated using this data. We require an algorithm that accurately extracts edge information from the image, and by accurately, we mean something that distinguishes between true edges and false edges, which may appear as a result of noise and texture in addition to displaying all edges that are there. As a result, we will utilize this information to give a weight in a manner that takes into account the fact that the human eye is more responsive to changes in areas with more edges than it is in those with fewer or no edges (smooth areas). This will be accomplished by utilizing an algorithm that has been developed by a number of authors and has proven to extract edges more effectively than the majority of previous edge detection techniques.

After applying a Gaussian or Laplacian filter to the image, there are numerous ways to identify edges based on a gradient of the image or zero crossings. Based on the phase congruency of feature detection, one of the best algorithms returns many more edges with good accuracy in identifying false edges. In contrast to most approaches, this one is invariant to image contrast. In order to calculate the major magnitudes of phase congruency moments, phase congruency is described as a dimensionless quantity that gives information that does not change with picture contrast. The greatest instant of phase congruency would be high at an edge.

We compute the normalized edge information for each of the blocks using a binary edge map and Equation (13).

$$M_E = \frac{64 * P_E}{\max(P_E)} \quad (13)$$

Where max is the highest value throughout the entire image, and P_E is the cardinality of the set of pixels at each block's edges.

Figure 3. Edge details of Cameraman and Lina image

Corner Information: Information about the corners is another crucial component in the pixel or spatial domain. For use in basic visual tasks, a number of methods have been proposed to detect corners, which have long been recognized as transmitters of visual information. Since an edge may only convey local information in one direction, normal to the edge, corners are thought to be more localized than edges and are therefore better at identifying the shapes of objects in photographs. The human eye is particularly sensitive to alterations made in corners because they represent the point where two edges converge. Perceptual watermark methods take into account uniformity as a crucial aspect of how people see things. To extract uniform regions, Kay and Izquierdo [30][37] [45] employ the Moravec operator. It is simply a corner detector that use a sliding window method to identify a block's smoothness through intensity change. The uniformity factor is defined as the number of pixels in a block that are part of a uniform area. However, because of its sensitivity to noise, a Moravec operator is discovered to be able to detect spurious corners, especially at isolated pixels. We will use a better corner detector to find the uniformity factor, which is correctly represented by the number of corners in a block. We need an algorithm that properly recognizes all the real corners that are present in a picture while decreasing the likelihood of finding false corners. There are various algorithms employing different ways to detect the right corners while removing the false corners. The method must be noise-resistant and the corner points must be accurately localized.

$$M_c = \frac{64 * P_c}{\max(P_c)} \quad (14)$$

Where max is the highest value across all blocks in the image, (P_c) indicates the cardinality of the set of pixels that are found to be corners in each block, and is the normalized value of the corner information.

Figure 4. Corner details of Cameraman and Lena image

The process of generating the just noticeable distortion mask is shown in Figure 5. The input cover picture is divided into 8X8 blocks in this process, and the edge, brightness, and corner coefficients are determined in the spatial domain for each block. These parameters are used to calculate J_i , which is an initial level mask as shown in Equation. (7)

Figure 5. Just Noticeable Distortion Mask Generation (JND) Process

Similarly, the parameter, M_T texture coefficient is calculated in frequency domain by converting all 8X 8 blocks into frequency components using 2D-DCT technique [41][28]. Hence obtaining these parameters such as edge coefficient (ME) luminance coefficient (ML), and corner coefficient (Mc) are carried out as mentioned in [42] [43]. The texture coefficient is determined in the frequency domain, while the aforementioned parameters are derived in the spatial domain.

3.3 Embedding Process:

This section provides a thorough presentation of the embedding process for the proposed work. The embedding of the watermark is done in frequency domain. Both the cover picture and the watermark image are inputs for the embedding procedure. The input image is transformed into 8X8 blocks, which are then utilized to create a distortion

mask with just enough apparent distortion. After all the final mask values have been determined, the watermark must be added [27] by identifying the 8x8 blocks' center frequency component. In addition, the watermark that needs to be added is translated into frequency components. The watermark bit is then multiplied by the scaling factor and the total of the final mask calculations [44]. Every block has been subjected to the inverse DCT in order to rebuild the watermarked image. In Figure 6, the embedding procedure is displayed. The algorithm for inserting a watermark is provided below.

Figure 6. Architecture of Watermark Embedding Process

Embedding-Algorithm $I(x, y)$, $W(x, y)$

Input image - $I(x, y)$ -

Watermark image - $W(x, y)$

*Step 1: Read $I(x, y)$ and size $N*N$*

*Step 2: Divide $I(x, y)$ into $8*8$ blocks to obtain N blocks*

Step 3: Apply 2D DCT on each block to calculate the AC & DC coefficient and Normalized texture coefficient.

For $K = 1$ to N

$K(u, v) = DCT2(k(x, y))$

Step 4: Calculate the Edge Coefficient for each 8X8 block in spatial domain

Step 5: Calculate the Luminance Coefficient for each 8X8 block in spatial domain

Step 6: Calculate Corner Coefficient for each 8X8 block in spatial domain

Step 7: Find Initial Mask based on Normalized Texture, Edge, and Corner Coefficient

Step 8: Generate the Final mask based on the Initial mask calculated and Luminance Coefficient

Step 9: Take a watermark image of size 256X256

- Step 10: Divide the watermark image into 8X8 block
- Step 11: Apply 2D DCT on each block for calculating AC& DC coefficient on the watermark image
- Step 12: Insert a watermark image in Cover Image 8X8 Block using a JND mask for the currently considered block
- Step 13: Repeat Step 3 to Step 12 for all remaining 8X8 blocks
- Step 14: Generate the watermark Bit for all blocks by multiplying the watermark bit and the Final mask coefficient, add it to the Cover Image
- Step15: Apply IDCT to achieve watermarked Image
- Step 16: Implement various attacks on watermarked image to check the robustness of the algorithm
- Step17: Measure the quality between the original and watermarked image (Use various metrics (SSIM, PSNR, SSI)
- Step 18: Divide Watermarked Image into 8X8 blocks for Watermark detection.
- Step 19: Apply DCT on each block extracted from watermarked Image
- Step 20: DCT coefficient of mid-band extracted by using inverse formula and IDCT
- Step 21: Implement various attack extracted watermarks and compare them with the original watermark
- Step 22: Original Watermark Image and Cover Image

3.4 Extraction Process

The watermark embedding process is logically reversed by the watermark extraction approach. The frequency domain watermark is retrieved from certain blocks when the watermarked encrypted image is deconstructed using the same s transform as when it was embedded.

Figure 7. Block Diagram of Watermark Extraction Process

Firstly, watermarked image is divided into an 8x8 block using the `mat2cell ()` function or `blockproc()` function in MATLAB. Applying DCT to an 8x8 block using the `dct2 ()` Frequency Domain Watermark function explained in the introduction part using a mathematical formula [47], depending on the algorithm, we get the result of a watermark bit wise and a cover image, as shown in Figure 7 [48-50]. The total watermark needs to be reconstructed at the end of the process.

Extraction-Algorithm: $(I''(p, q), I(p, q))$

Input Image: $I(p, q)$

Watermarked Image: $I''(p, q)$

Output Image: Extracted Watermark $W'(p, q)$

Step 1: Read Watermarked Image

Step 2: Apply Inverse 2D DCT to watermarked Image

Step 3: Utilize various assaults on watermarked photos to evaluate the algorithm's robustness.

Step 4: Compare the original and watermarked images' quality. (Use various metrics (SSIM, PSNR, SSI)

Step 5: To detect the watermark, divide the watermarked image into 8x8 blocks.

Step 6: Apply DCT on each block extracted from watermarked Image

Step 7: DCT coefficient of mid-band extracted by using inverse formula and IDCT

Step 8: Implement various attack extracted watermarks and compare them with the original watermark

Step 9: Original Watermark Image and Cover Image

4. Results and Discussion

The acquired outcomes of the suggested robust digital watermarking algorithm are thoroughly explored in this section. In order to implement a proposed work, a computing machine with the speed of 2.30 GHz, windows version 10 operating systems, 32 GB RAM and 1 TB Hard disk have been used. The Kodak dataset [51] and USI-SIPI datasets [52] were used to validate the suggested algorithm, and they are depicted in Table 1 and Table 2. Test cover images for the proposed method include Lena, Cameraman, Girl, F-16 plane, Boat, and Elaine. These pictures are all 256×256 pixels. Table 1 displays the test photographs. Table 2 provides various watermark pictures that were used to evaluate the suggested work and Table 3 provides watermarked images. We conducted an invisibility analysis using peak signal noise ratio (PSNR) and structural similarity index measure (SSIM) [10] as well as a robustness analysis using normalized coefficient (NC) [10] in order to assess and test the suggested approach. Table 4 displays the recommended method's robustness and invisibility on the Kodak and USI-SIPI datasets. The maximum PSNR value among the test photos was 56.1572 dB, and it is observed that the average PSNR value recorded for them was 55.7722 dB. Similarly maximum SSIM value among the test photos was 0.9985, and it is observed that the average SSIM value recorded for them was 0.9940. Additionally, in each scenario, the values of NC are getting 1. The Watermarked Images with Implementation of Some Attacks are shown in Table 5. Table 6 displays the NC values for the watermark pictures that were retrieved using various attacks. By comparing NC values under various attacks, which are shown in Table 7, the proposed method is also contrasted with the recent state-of-the-art algorithms for its performance in terms of resilience. It is clear from the data that the suggested strategy is resistant to various attacks. Furthermore when compared to several other pertinent techniques, Table 8 demonstrates that the obtained PSNR score performs better than the most recent ways.

Table 1. Sample cover images

<p>c) Elaine</p>		
<p>f) F16_Plane</p>		

Table 2: Sample Test Watermark Images

<p>c) Peppers</p>		
<p>f) Flowers</p>		

Table 3. Watermarked images

<p>a) Watermarked Image with rice Image as watermark</p>	<p>b) Watermarked Image with Pills Image as watermark</p>	<p>c) Watermarked Image with Peppers Image as watermark</p>
<p>d) Watermarked Image with Fish Image as watermark</p>	<p>e) Watermarked Image with Three_Trucks Image as watermark</p>	<p>f) Watermarked Image with Flowers Image as watermark</p>

Table 4. Evaluation of performance using the Kodak and USISIP datasets

watermarked Images	PSNR	SSIM	NC
Cameraman	55.7117	0.9985	1
Lena	56.1572	0.9904	1
Boat	55.0324	0.9904	1
Elaina	56.1001	0.9922	1
Girl	55.8797	0.9967	1
F16_Plane	55.7523	0.9962	1
Average score	55.7722	0.9940	1

Table 5. The Watermarked Images with implementation of some attack

Watermarked Image	Salt and Pepper Noise attack	Extracted watermark

Table 6. The retrieved watermark's NC for a suggested system under different attacks.

Attack	Lena	Cameraman	Elaine	Boat	Girl	F16 Plane	Average NC Score
Salt & pepper noise (0.01)	0.9976	0.9986	0.9976	0.9977	0.9983	0.9974	0.9978
Salt & pepper noise (0.02)	0.9848	0.9866	0.9844	0.9854	0.9882	0.9862	0.9859
Salt & pepper noise (0.05)	0.9672	0.9677	0.9678	0.9682	0.9654	0.9672	0.9672
Gaussian noise (M=0.1, var=0.01)	0.9966	0.9968	0.9972	0.9974	0.9976	0.9968	0.9970

Gaussian noise (M=0.1, var=0.2)	0.9724	0.9764	0.9744	0.9734	0.9734	0.9754	0.9742
Speckle noise (var=0.01)	0.9992	0.9988	0.9978	0.9988	0.9987	0.9988	0.9986
Speckle noise (var=0.02)	0.9868	0.9876	0.9866	0.9862	0.9863	0.9877	0.9868
Speckle noise (var=0.05)	0.9658	0.9658	0.9658	0.9658	0.9658	0.9658	0.9658
Gaussian filter (2, 2)	0.9988	0.9982	0.9982	0.9986	0.998	0.9978	0.9982
Gaussian filter (3, 3)	0.9956	0.9952	0.9954	0.995	0.9959	0.9958	0.9954
Median filter (2, 2)	0.9976	0.9978	0.9972	0.997	0.9976	0.9977	0.9974
Median filter (3, 3)	0.9955	0.995	0.9956	0.9958	0.996	0.9951	0.9955
Rotation	0.9922	0.9926	0.9923	0.9932	0.9933	0.9929	0.9927
Scaling	0.9944	0.9948	0.9952	0.995	0.9949	0.9942	0.9947
Cropping	0.7224	0.6924	0.6828	0.7212	0.699	0.6937	0.7019
JPEG2000 compression (5:1)	0.9972	0.9968	0.9967	0.9974	0.9971	0.9976	0.9971
Histogram Equalization	0.8896	0.8932	0.8898	0.8894	0.889	0.8892	0.8900
Line deletion	0.9272	0.9282	0.9281	0.9284	0.9284	0.9288	0.928183

Table 7. The comparative analysis of NC values of the proposed scheme

Attack	Proposed Scheme	Saxena Devi et al.[53]	Sharma et al.[54]	Anand et al.[55]	Mahto et al.[56]	Singh et al. [57]
Salt & pepper noise (0.01)	0.9978		0.9966	0.9687	0.9512	0.9834
Salt & pepper noise (0.02)	0.9859		0.9848			
Gaussian noise (M=0.1, var=0.01)	0.997				0.9581	
Gaussian noise (M=0.1, var=0.2)	0.9742	0.5136				
Speckle noise (var=0.01)	0.9986		0.9964	0.98		0.9839
Speckle noise (var=0.02)	0.9868		0.9848			
Speckle noise (var=0.05)	0.9658	0.9717				
Gaussian filter (2, 2)	0.9982					
Median filter (2, 2)	0.9974		0.9959		0.7282	
Rotation	0.9927		0.9914	0.9221		0.9985
Scaling	0.9947		0.9962			
Cropping	0.7019			0.5082		
JPEG2000 compression (5:1)	0.9971				0.6944	
JPEG30	0.9968	0.9784	0.9809	0.951		0.9994
Histogram Equalization	0.89			0.8716	0.8865	0.9117

Table 8. Comparison in terms of PSNR

	Imperceptibility Results (PSNR (dB))
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Performance measure	Proposed algorithm	Saxena Devi et al.[53]	Anand et al.[55]	Mahto et al.[56]	Singh et al. [57]
PSNR(in dB)	55.7722	48.522	38.3532	48.99	43.39

5. Conclusion

This work presents a powerful copyright protection method using grayscale images. Initially the suggested method divides the cover image into 8x8 blocks, then computes the brightness, edges, and corners coefficients in the spatial domain for each block. Each block of the cover image's texture coefficients is computed in the frequency domain. The distortion sensitivity of the image content is determined by reading the quilt item in each frequency and spatial domain. Local information this is derived from properties used to select a mask of only significant distinguishing values, such as texture, corner, area, and brightness. The proposed work provides thorough evaluation and implementation of content-based picture watermarking systems by analyzing the cover image in the frequency as well as the spatial domain. JND mask is determined using the local information received from features like texture, edge, corner, and brightness. It establishes the watermark's embedding strength. Canny is the edge detector operator which gives satisfactory results. The simulation results show that the recommended strategy has a high attacks resistance and strong imperceptibility. To demonstrate how the recommended research works better than current approaches, a thorough comparison is also carried out. The simulation demonstrates that the suggested approach outperforms the current techniques in terms of resilience and imperceptibility. In future, to increase performance, security, and capacity, we would like to evaluate the scheme's performance using AI/ML techniques in addition to encryption and compression techniques.

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